

DIVINFOOD

**Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains
to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food**

Deliverable D3.5

***SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use
benefits in farming, and empirical
data***

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 3.5. “*SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use benefits in farming, and empirical data*” of DIVINFOOD project presents the methodology that was used to assess the benefits of using agrobiodiversity in farming, and first empirical data. The assessment has been done within the framework of ecosystem services and through a participatory methodology implemented in the Living Labs (LLs) set up in the project. Results from this iterative process includes a list of SMART indexes which were co-designed by farmers, technicians, retailers, researchers, and other stakeholders involved in promoting neglected and underutilised crops (NUCs) at the local level. The SMART indexes presented in this deliverable, and related empirical data, will feed the database of the project, and will be used to help pilot farming, marketing and to favour responsible food choices.

To develop this deliverable, we have involved LL stakeholders, through a specific participatory workshop, to select Ecosystem Services (ES) delivered by genotypes in cultivation, with a large acceptance of ES including both ecological and socio-economic ones. Additionally, together with stakeholders along the value food chain, including farmers, we have identified the corresponding indicators that are easy to use in routine and that need a minimum of materials to assess, so that efficient monitoring can be processed with limited costs. An initial monitoring of selected ES indicators has taken place at different Living Labs in growing season 2 of the project, generating empirical data which are included in the deliverable.

From the on-farm trials and the reiterative deliberation of ES at the participatory workshop, this Deliverable presents a proposed set of 21 SMART indexes to guide for a minimum of 2 years of consecutive monitoring. These indicators are aimed to increase knowledge about the ability of NUC farming systems to provide ecosystem services.

Teams involved: Leader: (UEVORA) - Involved partners: AGRI KULTI, INRAE, ÖMKi, ICOEL, FIRAB, SLU, FiBL, BioCivam11

1. Introduction

This report presents the methodology that was used in the DIVINFOOD project to assess the benefits of using agrobiodiversity in farming, and first empirical data, from the example of NUCs. The assessment has been done within the framework of ecosystem services and through an innovative participatory methodology implemented in the Living Labs (LLs) set up in the project.

This report was delivered 1 month later than scheduled, due to internal peer revisions following the fine-tuning of the methodology to select the proposed indicators to be part of the SMART indexes for Ecosystem Services. This delay had no impact on the rest of the project.

1.1. Ecosystem Services (ES)

Daily (1997) defined an ecosystem as a community of organisms, their physical environment, and the interactions between them. Ecosystem services are the processes and conditions through which natural ecosystems and their species support human life. These services provide goods like food, timber, fibers, pharmaceuticals, and industrial materials, while also regulating weather, controlling erosion, and preventing floods and droughts.

In the latter half of the 20th century, ecosystem processes—such as water, nitrogen, carbon, and phosphorus cycles—underwent rapid changes. Human activities have altered not only the structure of ecosystems (e.g., species composition and habitats) but also their functions and processes, significantly affecting natural biogeochemical cycles and, consequently, the ability of ecosystems to provide services.

Ecosystem services offer various benefits (see Figure 1), including provisioning services (food, water, timber), regulating services (climate control, flood and disease prevention), cultural services (recreation, aesthetics, spiritual value), and supporting services (soil formation, photosynthesis, nutrient cycling). Despite technological and cultural buffers, humans remain deeply reliant on these ecosystem services.

Figure 1: The four main subsets of ecosystem services. Taken from Acheampong, M. (2020)

1.1.1. Ecosystem Services Frameworks

By categorising and organising ES benefits, frameworks help researchers, policymakers, and practitioners to better understand, assess, and manage ecosystem services. They provide a common language and frameworks for communication and decision-making. Additionally, different frameworks may emphasise different aspects of ecosystem services, reflecting the diverse perspectives and priorities of stakeholders involved in ecosystem management and policy. Different frameworks have been developed so far in the topic, such as:

- **TEEB (The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity):** TEEB is a global initiative focused on highlighting the economic value of ecosystem services and integrating this value into decision-making processes (TEEB, 2010).
- **Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA):** The MA was a landmark effort to assess the state of the world's ecosystems and their contributions to human well-being. It categorised ecosystem services into four broad categories (Table 1): provisioning, regulating, cultural, and supporting services (MEA, 2005).

Table 1: The four (4) Ecosystem Services proposed under the MA framework.

Ecosystem services	Description
Provisioning	These are the products obtained from ecosystems, such as food, water, timber, and medicinal plants.
Regulating	These are the benefits provided by ecosystems that regulate environmental conditions and processes, such as climate regulation, water purification, and pollination.
Cultural	These are the non-material benefits that people obtain from ecosystems, such as recreational opportunities, spiritual and cultural values, and aesthetic enjoyment.
Supporting	These are the services necessary to produce all other ecosystem services, including soil formation, nutrient cycling, and habitat provision.

- **Natural Capital Project:** This framework focuses on assessing the value of natural capital, including ecosystem services, to inform decision-making processes related to conservation and sustainable development (Tallis et al., 2010).
- **InVEST (Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs):** InVEST is a suite of tools developed by the Natural Capital Project for quantifying and mapping ecosystem services and their values.
- **IPBES (Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services):** IPBES provides assessments of the state of biodiversity and ecosystem services at the global level (IPBES, 2025).
- **CICES (Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services):** CICES provides a standardised way to classify and categorise ecosystem services, organising them into a hierarchical structure with multiple levels of detail (Czúcz et al., 2018).

1.1.2. Monitoring Ecosystem Services

Measuring ecosystem services is crucial for understanding the pressures on ecosystems, assessing their current state, and evaluating the impacts of human activities (Layke, 2009; Maes et al., 2016). The conceptual framework used in DIVINFOOD assumes that healthier, more resilient ecosystems—indicated by good environmental conditions—provide a greater array of services and retain their capacity to do so in the future (MAE, 2005).

Accurate measurement also supports the ongoing development of ecosystem accounts, as outlined in the [EU Biodiversity Strategy](#), and enhances the integration of ecosystem services into land, water, and urban management. Improved availability and usability of biodiversity datasets will further refine the mapping and assessment of ecosystem services, especially cultural services closely tied to biodiversity, such as birdwatching and the mapping of emblematic species.

However, challenges remain, including variations in data quality across pilot studies due to differing disciplinary approaches, and the often-overlooked influence of stakeholder values on ecosystem service assessments. Addressing these complexities is essential for the effective operationalization of ecosystem services in governance and decision-making processes (Locatelli et al., 2017).

In DIVINFOOD, we believe that monitoring ecosystem services is essential for several reasons. First, it provides a solid foundation to advocate for the inclusion of Neglected and Underutilised Crops (NUCs) in agricultural and food policies, presenting clear, evidence-based arguments to policymakers. Additionally, the results can highlight the ecological and socio-economic benefits of these crops, enhancing their market appeal and promoting their value to consumers. By using indicators, we can simplify complex ecological data, making it easier to communicate and understand. This allows policymakers to make informed, evidence-driven decisions, prioritize interventions effectively, monitor progress toward sustainability goals, and implement timely corrective actions when needed.

1.1.3. Participatory assessment of Ecosystem Services

Conducting a participatory assessment of Ecosystem Services is vital, as land use is a key driver of global environmental change and plays a critical role in sustainability efforts. Addressing the challenges linked to land use requires a fundamental societal shift, with input from science, politics, and the public to prevent crossing irreversible tipping points in global socio-ecological systems.

For transformative actions to be socially responsible and legitimate, they must balance diverse interests and demands on land use (Fabricius et al., 2007). This aligns with the goals of sustainability science (Bettencourt and Kaur, 2011), where researchers facilitate the co-design and co-production of knowledge alongside stakeholders to tackle pressing global issues. In this collaborative process, land use emerges as a focal point, as it encompasses critical human-nature interactions like biodiversity conservation, among many others.

Engaging stakeholders, particularly farmers, is crucial, as they possess valuable local knowledge and are directly responsible for implementing conservation measures. Often, the ecological reasoning behind such measures is not effectively communicated, reducing farmers' motivation and the success of these initiatives. A participatory approach ensures that policies and strategies are co-designed with those who are most affected, fostering greater acceptance and practical outcomes (Waltner-Toews et al., 2003).

Moreover, co-design enhances the development of indicators for ecosystem services, making them more intuitive, sensitive, and widely accepted (Layke, 2009). This participatory process not only increases scientific knowledge but also promotes co-learning through citizen science, ensuring that solutions are both evidence-based and grounded in real-world experiences.

Research in DIVINFOOD adopts Lang's (1998) food democracy perspective to carry out participatory research, which takes place within each Living Lab (Massari et al., 2022). For identifying cross-cutting ecosystem services indicators and monitoring measures, this inter- and transdisciplinary approach allowed to: (i) identify the values that should be prioritised when discussing crop varieties, on-farm diversification, production techniques, processing, and marketing practices; and to (ii) advance mutual learning, co-creation of knowledge, and the sharing of expertise at the Living Lab level.

1.2. SMART indexes

The use of genotypes (G) in food value chains is typically evaluated at the level of the agricultural plot, in relation to the biophysical environment and the agricultural practices implemented. DIVINFOOD extends the analysis of the benefits of using genotypes to the level of the food value chain and the Living Lab region.

Furthermore, the use of genotypes in food value chains is typically assessed through agronomic and technological criteria, so that the benefits of using genotypes are essentially measured through indicators related to productivity (e.g., yield) and technological quality (e.g., protein rate). The DIVINFOOD project assumes that using genotypes generates a larger range of benefits, not reduced to the criteria and indicators which are promoted in the agro-industrial system.

The DIVINFOOD approach thus broadens the analysis of genotype-environment interactions, both from the point of view of the environment considered and the results measured. The classic equation $G \times E = \text{yield and technological quality}$, where G = genetically homogeneous cultivars, and E = biophysical environment and agricultural practices, is here extended to $G \times E = \text{ecosystem services} + \text{other benefits} + \text{costs}$, where G = a diversity of genetic resources (pure lines, populations, landraces, etc.) and E = biophysical environment, agricultural practices, processing techniques, marketing channels, social organisations and regulations.

Finally, the impacts of genotype use are typically evaluated through indicators measured using tools available in the laboratory (e.g., NIRS method¹ to assess grain quality) and in relation to the

¹ NIRS stands for near infra-red spectroscopy, a technique used to measure fruit maturity.

objectives promoted in the agro-industrial system (maximisation of yield, technological parameters for industrial processing). DIVINFOOD seeks to evaluate these impacts through SMART indicators which can be measured, as far as possible, by easy-to-use methods. SMART indicators are specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound indicators that are used in monitoring and evaluation; they help to ensure that the indicators chosen are well-defined and can be effectively measured to track progress towards specific goals.

In the DIVINFOOD project, the specific goals are, on one hand, to develop healthy plant-based foods and environmentally, economically and socially sustainable food systems. On the other hand, the goal is to support professionals, decision-makers and citizens in evaluating by themselves, as far as possible, the impacts of using genotypes (i.e., growing a certain type of cultivar, e.g., population vs pure line of a certain type of crop, e.g., poulard wheat instead of common wheat) to facilitate the collective management and monitoring of agrobiodiversity. The indicators and measurement methods must therefore be chosen in relation to these goals.

In the field of agrobiodiversity, DIVINFOOD targets genotypes related to neglected and underutilised crops (NUCs). NUCs are those to which little attention is paid or which are entirely ignored by agricultural researchers, plant breeders and policymakers (Padulosi et al., 2002). The neglect of NUCs is partly due to their low competitiveness compared with major crops, so that they have not attracted the interest of those involved in the agro-industrial system. In this sense, NUCs are giving rise to alternative environments to the agro-industrial environment for the use of genotypes. The DIVINFOOD project aims to highlight the benefits associated with interactions between NUC genotypes and these alternative environments, throughout the value chains and at regional level. The objective is to propose SMART indicators to measure these benefits and to provide empirical data relating to these indicators.

A set of complementary deliverables presents the SMART indicators, and empirical data, related to the benefits resulting from the interactions between NUC genotypes and their environment of use in breeding (D4.3), farming (D3.5), food processing and eating (D2.3), and marketing (D1.4). All data are recorded in the database GxE developed in the WP5. Depending on the value chain stages, the proposed SMART indicators will not be fully measured in the time allotted to DIVINFOOD, but they are designed to be used by the actors involved in the field to evaluate and manage their activity around NUCs, and to compare the benefits gained from the use of these NUCs with those generated by major crops. This deliverable D3.5 is part of this set of deliverables and presents the SMART indicators and empirical data, related to the benefits, for the value chains and the regions, of using NUC genotypes in farming. In the case of this deliverable, benefits are classified into ecosystem services.

A final remark concerns the use of the term ‘indicator’, rather than the term ‘index’ mentioned in the DoA. The use of ‘index’ in the DoA was based on the idea that an index is intended to be easy to understand and useful for stakeholders (e.g., consumer price index). However, an index is also often understood as the synthesis of several indicators, which can ultimately limit its appropriation. We therefore finally opted for the term indicators, better understood by the living lab partners, even if some SMART indicators developed in the project are made up of several sub-indicators, and therefore can still be considered as indexes.

2. Methodology

This report focuses on the farm level. The objective was to assess the benefits of using NUCs at farm level, along an ecosystem services framework as expected in the Horizon 2020 topic to which DIVINFOOD proposed to respond. In line with the participatory research approach promoted in DIVINFOOD, the assessment of benefits of using NUCs in farming has been carried out with living labs' stakeholders, from the selection of the ES to be measured to their assessment.

2.1. Development of the participatory workshop for the selection of ecosystem services and indicators

For the participatory selection of ecosystem services and indicators to be measured in the NUC field by stakeholders participating in the different DIVINFOOD living labs, we decided to develop a half-day workshop dedicated exclusively to this task. The development of the workshop was an interactive and iterative process, to ensure it suited the objectives of the task and it could achieve the expected results. The steps were the following:

2.1.1 STEP 1. Selection of an Ecosystem Services framework

Within Work Package (WP) 3, in which this task has been carried out, a small expert panel was formed with researchers knowledgeable on ecosystem services, agronomy, and participatory methodologies to discuss the methodological process of this Task and to make decisions as informed as possible.

Since ecosystem services are complex and multifaceted, encompassing a wide range of benefits that ecosystems provide to humans, we needed to initially select an ES framework that served the purposes of DIVINFOOD.

The expert panel decided to use the CICES framework as basis to evaluate ecosystem services in a comprehensive and systematic way. We opted for this recent ES classification system as research has shown that it overcomes some misclassifications made in TAPE by FAO/TEEB (Czúcz et al., 2018) and is a reliable tool to understand the cross-cutting ways in which ecosystems contribute to human well-being. Moreover, this framework is also widely used in research, policy-making,

and natural resource management to assess and prioritise ecosystem services for conservation and sustainable use. The name of Ecosystem Services used in DIVINFOOD was adapted and harmonised for the project, based on CICES v.5 framework.

2.1.2 STEP 2. Pre-selection of ecosystem services and indicators by expert panel

Once it was decided by the expert panel that the CICES framework Version 5.1 was going to be used, the next step was to do a pre-selection of those ES that applied for the NUCs and work being done by stakeholders within DIVINFOOD Living Labs, especially by farmers who are the most concerned and knowledgeable about ES provided by using NUCs in farming. Considering the amount of work demanded from farmers who are part of DIVINFOOD, the expert panel did not want to overload farmers with having to monitor too many ecosystem services as well as all the other work demanded from the other project tasks. For this, we decided to find an equilibrium between meeting the objectives of the task, not overloading farmers, and developing a satisfying indicators matrix. Therefore, the initial list of CICES ES (86 ecosystem services) was shortlisted to the 8 most relevant ES based on the following criteria:

- Relevance to DIVINFOOD’s NUC;
- Existence of easy-to-use indicators to measure ES (not using complex lab measurements);
- Expert knowledge;
- Representativeness of all four (4) ES types (Table 1).

The description of each of these 8 ecosystem services was simplified to ensure all stakeholders could understand what these ES are and what they imply. An initial table containing the 8 ecosystem services and a list of indicators and ways to measure them was produced by the expert panel, as well as a selection of three (3) ES to be measured by all LLs to ensure a certain degree of comparability of the data, even if the final selection would be done by the LLs themselves. This list was then circulated amongst all DIVINFOOD consortium members so they could comment on the list, add ideas on indicators and easy ways/tools to measure those indicators. This table was circulated twice, and a final version containing 44 indicators was produced in February 2023. ES in green correspond to the mandatory indicators (see Table 2).

2.1.3 STEP 3. Structure of the ES participatory workshop

To meet the objectives of the workshop, we decided to create a board game to be played within each Living Lab that was named “Ecosystem Services Card Game”. Two versions of the same game were prepared: the main version for a face-to-face 1/2-day workshop and another version for an online workshop, in case any Living Lab could not carry it in person.

Both versions were developed with the following objectives:

- Present DIVINFOOD project’s general objectives;
- Present and discuss with participants the concept of ecosystem services;
- Co-develop a list of Ecosystem Services relevant for the LL;
- Select indicators and establish responsibilities for monitoring.

All final documentation and detailed instructions on how to carry out the workshop can be found in the annexes to this document. However, in Section 2 below we provide a short explanation of what was done. To refine the methodology of the workshop, we created a first version that was then circulated amongst WP leaders, it was then improved according to suggestions and presented to LL coordinators during a 2h online training session which took place on April 18th, 2023. Suggestions were again up taken to revisit and improve the methodology and produce another version, which was tested as a Pilot during the Annual DIVINFOOD Meeting in Portugal in May 2023. Results and evaluations were carried out produce the final materials that were provided to all LL coordinators to implement in their own living labs (see Figure 2).

Additionally, two (2) online meetings were carried out with our sister H2020 Project Radiant (*"RADIANT – Realizing Dynamic Value Chains for Underutilised Crops"*, <https://www.radiantproject.eu/>) to compare methodologies on Ecosystem Services measurement. These meetings took place the first trimester of 2023.

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Table 2: Matrix of indicators considered in DIVINFOOD for monitoring the contribution of NUC to ecosystem services.

*Compulsory ES and indicators are highlighted in green

Ecosystem Services		Description	Count of Indicators	Indicators	Way of determination
PROVISIONING	Food	Plants that are grown for food, resources, or energy	1	Grain yield	Measurement (t/ha) comparing different cultivars on the same field as well as comparing with main crop(s)
			2	Protein yield/content	Measurement (kg/ha or g/kg) comparing different cultivars on the same field as well as comparing with main crop(s)
			3	Edible yield	Measurement (kg/ha or g/kg) comparing NUC vs main crop
			4	Revenue for the farmer	
			5	Quantity for processing	
			6	Stability of yield, quality and demand	
REGULATING AND SUPPORTING	Genetic resources	The genes in plants and animals that are useful to humans are called the gene pool. It's important to keep a variety of different organisms, especially domesticated ones and their ancestors, to have a wide range of genes. The more diverse the genes, the better the ability to adapt to the environment.	7	Number of cultivated species at farm level within a calendar year	Self-declaration by the farmer (estimated number by the farmers across last 3-years)
			8	Number of cultivated NUC species at farm level within a calendar year	Self-declaration by the farmer (estimated number by the farmers across last 3-years)
			9	Number of genetically diverse NUC cultivars used within a calendar year	Number of landraces, populations, open pollinated varieties (everything that is not a hybrid or pure line variety)
	Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events (Water & soil conservation)	Plants on the ground stop the soil from washing away, which is important because when soil gets eroded, it becomes less fertile and can lead to the land becoming like a desert. This also makes it harder to grow crops.	10	Percentage of soil cover in cropland	Ratio of crop land with cover crop/winter crop/grassland and bare soil comparing NUC and main crop outside the growing season. What % and how many ha of the cultivated area is covered outside the growing season? Self-declaration of the farmer (% and ha)
			11	Soil cover duration	How many months of the year is the NUC and main crop covering the soil? Self-declaration of the farmer
			12	Type of tillage	What tillage systems are used in case of NUC and main crop production? Please indicate the % ratios. Low/minimum/zero/reduced
			13	Soil water retention capacity in agricultural soils	Soil infiltration test (https://www.wineaustralia.com/getmedia/ab39c37e-4644-4c0b-8f2-5ee05f6235ff/infiltration-rates.pdf) 2-Soil texture (manual) Sandy (no water retention) vs clayey (high capability to retain water) soils. 10.1016/j.geoderma.2015.12.022 3-Water retention at gravity (l) som content (qualitative with H2O2 test - bubbles see isbn 84-8476-231-9 page 122); and colour by Munsell chart (https://soils.uga.edu/files/2016/08/Munsell.pdf) Soil colour is defined by Hue/Value/Chroma. The levels of Value & Chroma < 3 indicates high content of som (qualitative).
			14	Use of agroforestry within floodplains	Agroforestry uses in case of NUC and main crop (yes/no) Estimation of the amount of biomass of NUC and main crop compared (estimation)
			15	Amount of biomass (C sequestration)	l) som content (qualitative with H2O2 test - bubbles see isbn 84-8476-231-9 page 122); colour by Munsell chart (https://soils.uga.edu/files/2016/08/Munsell.pdf) Soil colour is defined by Hue/Value/Chroma. The levels of Value & Chroma < 3 indicates high content of som (qualitative).
	Regulation of soil quality	Plants on the ground help keep the soil fertile by naturally adding nutrients like nitrogen and organic matter. They also protect the soil from getting polluted and help maintain its quality. Certain plants called legumes are used to increase or maintain nitrogen levels in the soil. Plants also play a role in forming and protecting soils and cleaning up contaminated soils and sediments.	16	Are there plant residues from previous year on cropland?	Yes/No (What do you do with the plant residues?) Spade diagnosis, earworm number/spade. Bait-Lamina Test for soil life indicator (http://www.terra-protecta.de/en/bait_strips.html#01) Mineralisation test (teabag, underwear or example from DIVERIMPACTS-->weaving frames). Weaving frames are very easy to use and should give quite standardized results. This is assessing the Mineral soil turnover, the rate on which mat. Org transforms into mat inorg (the one that the veg eats). It is related with water in soil, temperature in soil and microbiology. Earthworm diversity with eQBS. The rates are 1 tn/ha/year (as an average), one millimetre per ha per year. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2009.02.003
			17	Qualitative assessment of soil	Spade diagnosis, earworm number/spade. Bait-Lamina Test for soil life indicator (http://www.terra-protecta.de/en/bait_strips.html#01) Mineralisation test (teabag, underwear or example from DIVERIMPACTS-->weaving frames). Weaving frames are very easy to use and should give quite standardized results. This is assessing the Mineral soil turnover, the rate on which mat. Org transforms into mat inorg (the one that the veg eats). It is related with water in soil, temperature in soil and microbiology. Earthworm diversity with eQBS. The rates are 1 tn/ha/year (as an average), one millimetre per ha per year. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2009.02.003
			18	Fertilizer use	Qualification and quantification of fertilizer use
			19	pH of topsoil	Paper indicator
			20	Nitrogen provision (fixation)	2-NCI (E110) shows the basicity of the soil based on type of bubbles (isbn 84-8476-231-9 see page 108)
			21	Stone content	Evaluate N in the biomass, or the % cover only for legumes
			22	Bulk density	Sieving of soil samples Ring soil samples
			23	Simplified measurement of pollinators	E.g. count the number of insects trapped by a simplified trap (example from DIVERIMPACTS), if feasible identify the pollinator species
			24	Pollination potential	Measure seed set of a target plant e.g. sunflower
			25	Area coverage of flowering vegetation supporting pollination	Ratio of flowering vegetation to the total farm land (NUC and main crop separately)
	Pest, disease and weed control	Predators and parasites in ecosystems help control the populations of pests and disease carriers.	26	Flowering time	Time period in a calendar year with flowering plants present (NUC and main crop separately)
			27	Insect ground-nesting activity	Effective ground-nesting activity is assessed through counting n° of nests/area
28			Provided space for biological pest control (i.e., in corn vs wheat because of the plant density in the crop stand)	Count nesting birds on NUC and main crop field at a relevant time of the year	
29			Farming system	Type of plant protection used in case of NUC and main crop	
30			Saved costs on input purchase and hours/fuel/machinery for doing the treatments (€)		
31			Level of natural pest and disease resistance of NUC/main crop	Low, medium, high	
32			Qualification and quantification of plant protection used	Active ingredient and quantity used for NUC and for main crop	
33			Resistant and tolerant cultivars	Number of resistant/tolerant cultivars in case of NUCs and main crop separately used at farm level	
Habitat for species	Ecosystems provide homes for plants and animals and support a variety of important processes. Certain habitats have an abundance of species, making them genetically diverse and known as 'biodiversity hotspots'.	34	soil cover = competitive ability of cultivar against weeds and diseases (early plant vigour) > decrease of chemical weed control	At a relevant phase of the NUC as well as main crop, data will be collected separately on % crop cover / % weed cover / % bare soil (it can be more than 100%). At flowering and harvest. 1m2 area (at least 3 times): % crop cover / % weed cover / % bare soil (it can be more than 100%) Canopeo app can be applied for soil coverage, but it will not distinguish between crop and weed	
		35	Type, timing and application rate of phytosanitary products	Report for: insecticide, fungicide nematocide, herbicide. High doses & cocktails promote low biodiversity (and also health problems).	
		36	Ecosystem diversity. Presence of key wild plants (weeds)	Simple observation (can be done during an open field day involving all stakeholders) e.g., recording with the help of checklist and pictures easily recognisable key plant species, like paper at flowering period. Additionally, wild species can be measured via niche available for wild plants--> measured in artificial weed plot (e.g., a 1 qm of mixture of different species to mimic the wild plants)	
		37	Landscape Design/Colors		
CULTURAL	Millions of people around the world are drawn to enjoy nature, which provides cultural benefits to visitors and income opportunities for those in the nature tourism industry.	38	Target species in the region		
		39	Diversity in insects, animals, birds		
		40	The requirement of the habitat. Balance with crops.		
		41	NUC events as income opportunities for farmers cultivating NUCs	Events related to NUC (number of events, revenue of the events, number of visitors, number of jobs created).	
		42	Cultural value	Number of NUC crops added in the cropping system Number of heritage cultivars/landraces added in the cropping system.	
		43	Funding opportunities, as income opportunities for farmers cultivating NUCs	Funding (Number of Research projects, rural development funds, other funds, other advantages like direct marketing, related to NUC, number of jobs created. Compare with main crop.	
		44	Learning (human capital) by doing		

Figure 2: Methodological process for the development of the participatory ES workshop.

2.2 Training of the trainers: ES participatory workshop in DIVINFOOD

The materials that were developed and provided to LL coordinators to carry out the participatory workshop (Annex 1) included:

1. **ES Matrix Indicators table.** Simplified table of Ecosystem Services_Indicators with support information for the facilitators to use if needed.
2. **Roadmap/instructions.** Document for the Workshops with detailed steps for the ES card game.
3. **Material** for the ES game:
 - a. ES Cards (in EN)
 - b. Template sheet to rank ES
 - c. Large poster for voting on ES
2. Template tables for the selection of indicators
3. **PPT** presentation with some ES examples to use during the workshop (optional)
4. Simple **Reporting Template**
5. **Attendance Form**
6. Ecosystem Services_ **Workshop Assessment** <https://forms.gle/fwu24a2ReA7oTAUNA>

Additionally, after the request of some LL coordinators, who worried the concept of ecosystem services could be hard to grasp in a workshop and asked for an additional activity to transfer this knowledge, we developed a pre-workshop game we called “Treasure Hunt”. Its objective was to introduce ES so that stakeholders would become familiar with the concept and be able to observe *in loco* what they represent. This activity was optional and only to be used when LL coordinators deemed it necessary.

During the “Treasure Hunt” activity, the LL coordinators provided participants with an introduction to the concept of Ecosystem Services (ES) in a straightforward manner, highlighting the benefits and illustrating the unique characteristics of ES in each specific location. Following this introduction, coordinators distributed game sheets to all participants (Figure 3). These sheets contained questions related to the observation and identification of various elements representing ES within the field environment. Participants then had a designated time frame to explore the field, seeking out and observing elements that relate to ES as indicated on their game sheets. They could choose to fill in their sheets with the identified elements or to take photographs of them and send these images, properly labelled, back to the LL coordinator. The participant who completed the exercise first, either by filling in their sheet or submitting the required photographs, was declared the winner and received a symbolic prize.

Once all participants have completed their exploration, they gathered in a group setting to share the results of their "treasure hunt." This activity allowed for a collaborative discussion where participants could compare their findings, exchange insights, and deepen their understanding of ES within the context of the field environment.

Figure 3: Example of Treasure Hunt field sheets

2.2.1 Pilot test of ES participatory workshop

A pilot test was carried out in DIVINFOOD First Annual Meeting in Alvaiázere (Portugal) in May 2023 (Figure 4). The purpose of this session was to experiment and refine the participatory workshop methodology and materials. These tools would be used by the LL coordinators to dynamise similar sessions to choose the Ecosystem Services (ES) that will be measured in each Living Lab (LLs).

During the annual meeting, the Workshop had the active participation of 22 partners who were divided into 5 working groups. These groups engaged in discussions and prioritised the ES based on their level of significance. Additionally, they incorporated indicators and methods for measuring the ES that could be implemented in the LLs, upon the co-definition process derived from the ES workshop.

Figure 4: Pictures from the pilot test carried out in DIVINFOOD's first annual meeting (May 2023)

2.2.2 Ecosystem Services (ES) Card Game

The materials developed for Task 3.3 were designed to offer ideas and guidance on conducting a participatory workshop for selecting Ecosystem Services and their indicators. The goal of the workshop is to facilitate a collaborative process that results in a co-created list of SMART indicators. Figure 5 below provides an idea of the roadmap and times for the different phases of the workshop.

Figure 5: Workshop Roadmap (half a day)

PHASE 1. Participants are divided into small groups (divided by sector of activity):

- I. The cards are laid out on the table and the **facilitator explains the content of each card/ES and which ES will be considered "compulsory" for measurement in the project (Compulsory ES are marked with a star (*) on the cards).**
- II. Each participant has 5 minutes to see the cards and make a list (on a sheet provided for this purpose) in which they prioritise the cards according to relevance.
- III. Each participant shares their list with the group and explains the reasons for their choice. At the end, all participants agree on a final list.

Figure 6: Examples of the Cards developed for each Ecosystem Service. Card marked with a star correspond to the ES selected by the Expert Panel as mandatory to be monitored in all LLS.

Figure 7: Workshop materials (cards and voting table) translated into Portuguese, as used during the Ecosystem Services workshop at Gpea LL (24 January 2024).

PHASE 2. Back in plenary Discussion

- I. Table facilitators present the results of their tables and a summary of the discussion.
- II. The main facilitator presents the ES list on a large poster placed on the wall of the room **(separating compulsory ES from non-compulsory ES - Compulsory ES are marked on the table)**
- III. Each LL participant will be given 2 votes (colour stickers) to vote on those non-mandatory services they believe are most important/relevant for the ecosystem.
- IV. The 2 most voted ES, together with the 3 compulsory ES are those that will be used for indicator selection (3rd part).

Figure 8: Example of the ES Cards and individual coloured voting markers to select ES based on relevance.

Figure 9: Voting of ecosystem services' order of relevance, in relation to grain legumes cultivated in Switzerland. Photo from the ES workshop at LL Leg-Switz (01 December 2023)

PHASE 3. World Café Method

- I. Organise participants in 4 to 5 tables. Important! each table will work on 1 of the selected Ecosystem Service (top 3 or 4 of the ES).
- II. Table facilitator places the provided ES table with indicators (2d_Template_Table Indicators) on the table, which is already prefilled with indicators (**some are compulsory too - Compulsory ES Indicators are marked on the table**).
- III. Each participant is provided with a few post-it notes to think and write other ideas of indicators that could be used to measure each ES (each participant writes one idea per post it). Participants can also write directly on the template table.
- IV. Discussion goes around on which indicators would be best or easier to measure. Facilitators take notes on the discussion to present it to the next group.
- V. 3 rounds of 15 to 20 min. Participants change table and can freely decide which table to go to, always making sure all tables are covered.

Note: Indicators should be **easy to use** on a day-to-day basis and need a minimum of materials to assess the criteria, so that efficient monitoring can be processed with limited cost.

Option 2. LL coordinators could also opt to do this part without people rotating tables and having a longer discussion in each table and various indicators per table. (Note: replicate the same method as it was used during the first annual meeting).

PHASE 4. In plenary session

1. Table facilitators present in plenary session the result of each table (indicators and ways of measuring them).
2. The main Facilitator in the plenary session asks participants who (which farmers) would be interested in measuring these ES and which ones? (facilitator should aim to have different farming systems).
3. Facilitator records names of responsible people.

3. ES workshops in DIVINFOOD Living Labs

3.1 Implementation of the workshops

The Ecosystem Services workshops took place between September 2023-November 2024 in eight (8) Living Labs participating in the DIVINFOOD project (Table 3). On the grounds of logistics, workshop development varied from context to context. For instance, LL CerOcc (LL3) was unable to organise the ES workshop due to the lack of availability of farmers and a lack of foresight by the LL coordinator. However, an informal and brief discussion on specific ecosystem services was held at another meeting within this lab, and will be valued in the database of the project (WP5).

LL Faba-Nord (LL6) and LL Leg-Nord (LL7) organised a joint ES workshop to increase stakeholder participation and ease preparatory work. This made sense given the geographical proximity of the actors. Similarly, Leg-It-Switz (LL4) opted for holding two separate workshops to examine the Italian and the Swiss realities individually to discuss the specific needs at each context.

Figure 10: Ecosystem Services workshop at the Faba/Leg-Nord LLS (05 November 2024).

In general, all eight (8) ES workshops were deemed productive and useful to discuss the importance of ecosystem services at each locale. Discussions centred around the awareness of these services by farmers, even if implicit and non-theoretical, although issues were reported in deciding the order of relevance of ES. In some of the LLS, workshop participants found it challenging to rank the ES, as all were claimed to be relevant and interconnected with one another (LL1, LL4, LL6, LL7, LL8). The ‘chicken and egg’ metaphor was brought up in the LL6/LL7 workshop, as a form to explain how ES are interdependent and their effect can only be understood as a system. Farmers new to NUC farming found it difficult to assess what ES were relevant or not (LL1), arguing that it takes time to evaluate the benefits of crops.

Challenges were also raised regarding the comparability of the assessment methods. Participants of LL5 workshop suggested establishing a partnership between producers and researchers to do a test with and without rotation in areas with and without NUC, to assess the intensity of natural pest infestation. In LL1, participants recommended measuring the pH of topsoil using a paper indicator in both the NUC plot and a comparative off plot section.

Table 3: Summary of the ES services workshops carried out in DIVINFOOD LLS.

LL code	Living Lab Name	Country	NUC	Workshop data (DD/MM/YY)	N°. of participants	Notes
LL1	Bean_Lyon	France	meat bean	26/01/2024	9	
LL2	Bean_Cast	France	lingot bean	21/04/2024	6	
LL3	Cer-Occ	France	einkorn, rivet wheat			No workshop was carried out.
LL4	Leg-It-Switz	Italy	white lupin	08/11/2023	9	LL4 carried out two independent ES workshops, according to each national section.
	Leg-It-Switz	Switzerland		01/12/2023	15	
LL5	Gpea	Portugal	grass pea	31/01/2024	12	

LL6	Faba-Nord	Denmark	faba bean	05/11/2024	17	LL6 and LL7 carried out one joint ES workshop to maximise stakeholder contribution.
LL7	Leg-Nord	Sweden	narrow-leaved lupin, grey pea, lentils			
LL8	Leg-Hung	Hungary	common bean, lima bean, cowpea, chickpea, lentil, grass pea, adzuki bean, mungbean	12/09/2023	17	
LL9	Cer-Hung	Hungary	einkorn; emmer	06/03/2024	8	
Total					93	

Difficulties were also identified in terms of fulfilling the workshop proposed tasks and meeting the objectives. Due to time constraints, often because the workshops were scheduled around other Living Lab-related activities, some of the workshops did not use the ES card game (3 out of the 8 workshops). Instead, a plenary discussion among participants to deliberate the ecosystem services was opted for. This did not impede the convergence of ideas, the ranking of ES, and the compilation of new indicators and methods to measure the services. More details on the learnings and results from this co-design process is found under section 4.

Figure 11: Ecosystem Services workshop at Leg-Switz LL (01 December 2023).

A total of 93 participants took part of the ES workshops. Stakeholder representation was homogenous across the workshops, with a slight lower number of producers (including farmers and gardeners) than research institutions (Figure 12). This might be explained from the purposeful selection of participants invited to the workshops, which sought to collect the knowledge from farmers and experts in a specific subject (i.e., agronomists, soil scientists, etc.).

Producers’ cooperatives and associations included collective businesses (e.g., seed breeders/suppliers). Under the Companies/Retailers category mostly processors were reported. As ‘other’ were included a workshop facilitator and an independent technical advisor. No representation from the local/regional/national authorities was found.

Figure 12: ES workshop participants by category.

In terms of gender representation, 53% of participants were male and 40% were female (see Figure 13).

Figure 13: ES workshop participants, by gender (%)

3.2 Results: ranking of Ecosystem Services

The participatory workshops for selecting Ecosystem Services (ES) served to revise the proposed list of indicators that had previously been developed in DIVINFOOD to measure the ES resulting from agrobiodiverse farming systems (see Step 2 of the Methodology in Section 2.1.2). These workshops sought to raise awareness about ES, facilitate a collaborative process to discuss their relevance and ways to measure, and to co-develop a list of SMART indicators.

The perceived relevance of the ES was based on the ranking exercise at the participatory workshops done in the discussion groups including farmers (hereafter referred to as ‘producers’), although relevant discussions in groups with other actors took place and were relevant in the final selection of indicators. We opted to prioritise farmers’ perceptions over other actors’, because the goal of this Deliverable is to select ES indicators that make sense and are easy to measure by farmers mainly.

From the ranking of the eight (8) ES (see Table 4), we learnt that workshop participants regard ES differently across the LLs, although some commonalities were also found. Even though workshops stressed the importance of all ES, participants expressed heightened relevance of some services over others. Differences could be explained because of the diverse farming systems in DIVINFOOD, despite they are cultivating at least one type of NUC, whereas similarities could stem from the perceived interest for promoting these varieties at each context. Some LLs did not include some ecosystem services in the voting, thus leaving placements 7 and 8 in the order of relevance with only 6 votes (Table 4). In sum, the order of relevance of ES, as perceived by farmers, from high to low, came up to be as follows:

1. Food
2. Regulation of soil quality
3. Genetic resources
4. Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events
5. Pollination
6. Habitat for species
7. Pest, disease and weed control
8. Cultural services

Food came up as the most relevant ES perceived by farmers in the workshops. Some of the reasons given included the essentiality of food to human life (LL1, LL2, LL5, LL6, LL7, LL8), the potential alternative uses of NUCs as forage and cover crop (LL4 Leg-It, LL8), and the nutritional value of NUCs (LL4 Leg-It, LL6, LL7), especially the high protein content (LL4 Leg-Switz, LL8).

The *regulation of soil quality* was identified as the second most relevant ES for farmers. At the LL5 workshop, producers stated that “one must deal with what needs fixing first to then deal with producing [NUCs] after”. Special attention required for guarding soil health was also stressed by producers in LL1, including its resistance capacity to disease and frost, which was said to impact the physical-chemical quality of the NUC. Other arguments supporting this ES relevance included the capacity of legumes to provide deep root systems and to improve humus and soil structure (LL1, LL4 Leg-Switz), to enhance nitrogen fixation (LL5, LL8, LL9), and in reducing greenhouse gases emission and global warming (LL9).

Table 4: Number of votes of perceived relevance of ES by producers in all eight (8) ES workshops.

Ecosystem Services	Ranking (high to low)							
	i	ii	iii	iv	v	vi	vii	viii
Food	4	1	2	0	0	1	0	0
Genetic resources	1	2	1	3	1	0	0	0
Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	1	1	2	0	2	0	1	0
Regulation of soil quality	2	3	0	1	0	2	0	0
Pollination	0	1	2	2	1	1	0	0
Pest, disease and weed control	0	0	1	0	1	1	4	0
Habitat for species	0	0	0	2	1	3	1	0
Cultural services	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	6
<i>Total votes in LL workshops</i>	8	8	8	8	8	8	6	6

Genetic resources was the third most voted ES by producers. This service was deemed essential for providing upcoming generations with a gene pool as large as possible amidst current global challenges (LL5, LL6, LL7) and for plant's resilience (LL5), because "if there is more diversity, there is more adaptability" (LL1). Genetic diversity was also argued to be important for food autonomy (LL1) and in search of novel cultivars to make the crop attractive and viable (LL2).

The *regulation of baseline flows and extreme events* came up in fourth place, yet its interconnection with soil quality was stated (LL1). The major problem mentioned regarding this service was protecting water quality, to which trees and hedges were said to help in water retention (LL1). Participants of LL8 workshop argued that legumes are important cover crops that promote deep root systems and can help in the adaptability to climate change. In mountain soils, this ES was considered relevant for erosion control, sloping grounds, and in risk of gulying, etc. (LL1). The agronomical value of legumes in the farm system was also referred to as an important reason of this ecosystem service (LL2).

Pollination came in fifth place. This ES was associated with productivity, because "if there is no pollination, there will be no fruit and no food" (LL1). This service was deemed relevant for improved biodiversity (LL4 Leg-Switz) and to keep and propagate cultures (LL5, LL6, LL7). Legume flowers were considered important because they attract bees and other pollinating insects (LL8), as reported by farmers after switching to organic farming (LL1), and especially relevant in late flowering seasons for an extended pollination period (LL4 Leg-Switz).

The ecosystem service *habitat for species* (place 6) received one argument for its relevance, which appears somehow counterintuitive. Farmers argued that the lupin's bitterness was useful to deter attacks by wild animals (LL4 Leg-Switz), making the environment unsuitable for unwanted animals in their fields/gardens. This claim, however, does not necessarily align with what the literature supports about this ES.

Pest, disease and weed control (place 7) was argued to be relevant for crop rotation, to understand the cycle and disease breakouts in soil and to see the mosaic of crops (LL5).

The last ES, *cultural services* (place 8), was deemed relevant for participants in LL2 workshop, especially for the local economy, and for territorial promotion (LL4 Leg-It, LL5). The symbolic touristic attractiveness and gastronomic value were some of the arguments provided.

We weighted the ranking of votes per ES, according to their order of relevance, to then attain the weighted mean value for each service. These weighted mean values served to compare the relevance of each ES, as voted in the participatory workshops (Fig. 14).

Figure 14: Relevance of the Ecosystem Services, as perceived by group 'producers'.

3.3 Selection of indicators to measure Ecosystem Services

Beside ranking the Ecosystem Services, participants also discussed during the workshops the theory-based and peer-reviewed list developed among DIVINFOOD partners, which was used during the ES workshops (Table 2). While some of the indicators seemed obvious to participants, a few were phrased differently, new indicators were proposed, different measurements were suggested to ease assessment, whereas other indicators were ignored. However, it is important to highlight that three (3) ES indicators were mandatory for discussion (and consequently, for field monitoring) at the workshop, which might help explain the results from the workshops.

From the initial matrix of 44 indicators provided to ES workshop participants (Table 2), 23 new indicators were suggested by participants, whereas 16 new measuring techniques were proposed to assess the ES. This addition brought the total number of indicators to 76. The new indicators were proposed under the ES food (8x), followed by genetic resources (7x), regulation of soil quality (5x), regulation of baseline flows and extreme events (2x), and pollination (1x). However, some of these new indicators were suggested in more than one workshop. One (1) indicator under ES food was proposed four times, one (1) under ES genetic resources repeated three times, and another one (1) indicator under ES food came up twice. Figure 15 presents the distribution of the new indicators, across the Ecosystem Services.

Figure 15: Count of new Ecosystem Services indicators, as proposed in the ES workshops.

Table 5 below shows the distribution of all 76 indicators discussed during the ES workshops, according to the count in each ES. The count refers to the number of LL that deemed a specific indicator useful, or not, to assess an ecosystem service in their territory. As shown, 21 indicators were disregarded among workshop participants, showing 0 votes, with many indicators under ES habitat for species, followed by pest, disease and weed and control and then, cultural services. Similarly, 34 indicators were validated once, presenting 1 vote. Notably, 1 indicator was validated in all 7 workshops, under the ES food, and 2 indicators came up 6 times, under the ES: food and regulation of soil quality. The recurrence of indicators in 2, 3 and 4 occasions presented a much lesser count.

Table 5: Global count of voted indicators across the Ecosystem Services.

Ecosystem Services	Count of voted indicators							Total
	0	1	2	3	4	6	7	
Food		10	2		3	1	1	17
Genetic resources		6		2	2			10
Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	1	4	2	1				8
Regulation of soil quality	2	5	1	2	1	1		12
Pollination	2	3	1					6
Pest, disease and weed control	5	2	1					8
Habitat for species	8	2						10
Cultural services	3	2						5
<i>Total</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>34</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>76</i>

The absence of some of the indicators proposed, the suggestion of new indicators and methods for assessment, and the reoccurrence of some of them hint at the similar perceptions of workshop participants across the participatory workshops in the seven (7) LLs. This process served to validate and improve the initial list of proposed ES indicators and to help construct a revised list of SMART indexes to assess ES.

Figure 16 includes the summary of the results from the ES workshop discussions. Axis x presents the relative relevance of ES, based on the weighted average values from the ranking of the

Ecosystem Services. Axis *y* shows the number of indicators per ES, as discussed among workshop participants.

Figure 16: Summary of results from the ES workshops.

4. Field monitoring and ES data collection

The first monitoring of Ecosystem Services was carried out in parallel with the on-farm trials from DIVINFOOD LLs during growing season 2 (Szira et al., 2024). The eight (8) mandatory ES indicators required for this initial data reporting are presented in Table 6, based on the matrix proposed in Step 2 of the methodology.

In total, data on ES indicators were collected in 27 on-farm trials across seven (7) LLs for season 2 (Annex 2). Data collection expressed the large diversity of the trials, considering characteristics such as the cultivar type, cropping method, and plant density. The idea was to compare the ES delivered by farms using NUCs in agroecology with farms using simpler rotations (LL4 Leg-Switz), as well as in farms cultivating NUCs with various plant densities (LL6/LL7).

Empirical data collected on ES was initially homogenised to ensure quality and compatibility. All reported yield values were converted to kg/m² and entries with no data were also discarded. The summary of data collected from the on-farm trials is presented in Annex 2. At the end, 37 on-farm datasets were considered valid on three (3) ES indicators:

- NUC yield (kg/m²);
- number of cultivated NUC species at farm level within a calendar year; and,
- weed coverage of NUC area around harvest (%).

Table 6: List of mandatory ES indicators from which data was collected in the on-farm trials for season 2.

Ecosystem Services	Indicators
Food	NUC Yield (t/ha or kg/m ²)
Genetic resources	Number of cultivated species at farm level within a calendar year
	Number of cultivated NUC species at farm level within a calendar year
	Number of genetically diverse NUC cultivars used within a calendar year
Pest, disease and weed control	Weed coverage (%) of the NUC area during early plant development
	Weed coverage of the NUC area around harvest (%)
	NUC Soil coverage 1. / NUC Early plant vigour (%)
	NUC Soil coverage 2. / NUC Biomass (%)

These indicators were identified as the easiest to measure and to report at the farm-level, and thus suggested to be included in the SMART index table of ES to assess agrobiodiversity (see Section 7).

In DIVINFOOD, we will take the opportunity to collect more solid data in the upcoming on-farm trial seasons (3 and 4), based on the SMART indexes deriving from this Deliverable. New comparable data on the monitoring of ES will be updated in the GxE database within WP5 of the project.

5. SMART indexes table for Ecosystem Services

This section presents a SMART indexes table with the Ecosystem Services, indicators, and easy-to-measure methods to assess the effect of NUC farming systems on agrobiodiversity, which was co-developed among farmers, LL stakeholders, and knowledge brokers. The SMART indexes table is composed of 21 ES indicators and contemplates all eight (8) ecosystem services, including:

- a) the three (3) indicators identified as useful to measure during the on-farm trials in season 2 (see Section 4), plus,
- b) the most relevant ES indicators, as perceived by farmers and other stakeholders during the ES workshops (see Section 3.2).

Most relevant indicators were selected and ordered according to their occurrence in the workshop discussions and the relative weight of each ES derived from the ranking exercise. The number of indicators per service in the SMART index table is presented in Table 7.

The SMART indexes table aims to help stakeholders identify ES at field and landscape level, in complementarity with farmers, who can assess this more specifically at the plot level. For this reason, some of the measuring techniques were adapted from the initial ES matrix, contemplating the input from the ES workshops. The criteria to choose an easy-to-measure method to assess each indicator in the SMART indexes list were:

1. It can be measured by farmers and/or other stakeholders (lab work was considered an option only if deemed an essential ES indicator (aka. the ES indicator had a high voting count));
2. It was validated during the ES workshops and the field trials (season 2);
3. It represents a low or no cost for the farmers and stakeholders.

Table 7: Distribution of the ES indicators in the SMART index table.

Note: The total weighted average value is below 1.0 because two (2) workshops reported only five (5) ES in the ranking exercise.

Ecosystem Services	ES indicators		ES ranking		SMART indexes
	Count	%	weighted average value	%	N°. of indicators
Food	17	22	0.160	19	4
Genetic resources	10	13	0.146	17	3
Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	8	11	0.108	13	3
Regulation of soil quality	12	16	0.156	18	4
Pollination	6	8	0.101	12	2
Pest, disease and weed control	8	11	0.066	8	2
Habitat for species	10	13	0.073	9	2
Cultural services	5	7	0.055	5	1
<i>Total</i>	<i>76</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>0.864</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>21</i>

As result, a revised SMART indexes table includes a clear set of indicators and easy to measure techniques to facilitate the assessment of NUC farming effects on agrobiodiversity (Table 8). It can be used by NUC farmers and stakeholders and in support with research units.

Table 8: SMART index table of ES indicators to assess agrobiodiversity, as proposed in DIVINFOOD.

SMART index (n°.)	Ecosystem service	Indicator	Assessment method
1	Food	Revenue for the farmer	Self-reported by farmer.
2		NUC yield	Measurement comparing different cultivars on the same field (kg/m2).
3		Stability of yield, quality, and demand	Self-reporting of yield and quality, average and variance between years (by farmer, processors, traders). Alternatively: report number of sales contracts.
4		Protein content in yield	Lab work to measure the chemical composition and nutritional value of cooked NUC.
5	Genetic resources	Number of cultivated NUC species at farm level within a calendar year	Self-reporting by the farmer.
6		Plot size per species as a proportion of total area	Estimate size of plot size in comparison with total area (%).
7		Number of crop rotation components: crop rotation benefits, composition	Farmer(s) assesses how many elements are sown in 1 year.
8	Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Retention capacity of water in agricultural soils	Measure using a simple soil moisture tool.
9		Soil cover duration	Measure soil cover duration using Canopeo app, mark in the calendar and take pictures.
10		Type of tillage	Self-reporting of fuel savings on machinery (euros/year).
11	Regulation of soil quality	Nitrogen provision (fixation)	Soil analysis laboratory: Nitrogen (N) content.
12		Plant residues from previous year on cropland	Measure weight of residues/m2 (kg).
13		Fertilizer use	Self-reporting of name and quantity of fertiliser used in the field.
14		pH of topsoil	Use a simple paper indicator.
15	Pollination	Simplified measurement of pollinators	Count the number of insects trapped by a simplified trap. If feasible, identify the pollinator species.
16		Number of cultivated species that require pollination	Farmers count the n° of the different species cultivated that reproduce via pollinators.
17	Pest, disease and weed control	Level of natural pest and disease resistance of NUC/main crop	Partnership between farmers-researchers: Do a test with and without rotation in areas with and without NUC. Observe the intensity of the infestation and report (low, medium, high).
18		Soil cover. Competitive ability of cultivar against weeds and decrease of chemical weed control	Visual measurement using guide sheet "Weed coverage". Phenological stage for cereals: Zadocks growth scale 41-69, legumes: BBCH-scale for legumes 50 -69).
19	Habitat for species	Flower strips	Count of the flower strips planted in between the crops (producers).
20		Permanent habitat for insects	Count the existing sites where insects can eat and reproduce (producers).
21	Cultural services	NUC events as income opportunities for farmers cultivating NUCs	Report the number of events related to the NUC per year in the territory (local, regional, national).

6. Conclusion

Recognition about the value and urgency to protect Ecosystem Services through sustainable farming systems amidst the current climate crisis was confirmed by farmers and stakeholders participating in the ES workshops and throughout the activities pertaining to this task. An easy-to-use toolkit to measure ES was welcomed by workshop participants to increase knowledge about the ability of NUC production systems to provide ecosystem services.

The co-development of a set of SMART indexes to assess the benefits of using agrobiodiversity in farming within DIVINFOOD resulted from an iterative process that included various actors along the food value chain: farmers, technicians, retailers, researchers, and other local actors involved in the promotion of NUC across the Living Labs involved. It consisted of a complex co-design process of nearly 24 months that started from the selection of up-to-date scientific knowledge on ES indicators, which first underwent revision within the project consortium, to later be validated by farmers and other stakeholders in an Ecosystem Services workshop. The final selection of ES indicators included in the SMART indexes table included in this Deliverable was produced using statistical analysis of the data collected in the ES workshops and on-farm trials. For all SMART indicators, easy-to-use methods to measure them are proposed, from a literature review, empirical data collection, and discussions in the workshops.

From the ES participatory workshops, we confirmed the arguments supported by the scientific literature about cultural services, which are still perceived as less significant in comparison to other ES contributing to biodiversity. Any territorial efforts towards the promotion of NUC cultivation, market access and climate change mitigation are to invest in reverting this trend considering rural development and more sustainable food production methods.

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8. Annexes

8.1 Annex 1: Materials developed and used in all Living Labs for the ES participatory workshop

8.1.1 Workshop Roadmap

This document and all the material that has been developed for task 3.3 is meant to help you and provide you with ideas and orientations towards how you can develop a workshop in which Ecosystem Services and their indicators are selected in a participatory manner. It is very important that you return the Reporting Document with all the necessary information filled out once you have carried out the workshop. This activity has been planned for a group of around 15-20 people. You can adjust accordingly.

Workshop Objectives:

1. Present the DIVINFOOD project's general objectives
2. Present and discuss with participants the concept of ecosystem services
3. Select the main Ecosystem Services relevant for the LL
4. Select indicators and establish/determine responsibilities

TIMELINE to carry out the Workshop

Deadline: October 2023

MATERIAL YOU ARE PROVIDED WITH:

This document, which is a roadmap/instructions for the Workshops with detailed steps for the ES card game (1_Workshop Roadmap)

1. Material for the ES game:
 - a. ES Cards (in EN, they will have to be translated) (2a_PPT_ES CARD GAME) **(must be saved in PDF and printed in color front and back)**
 - b. Template sheet to rank ES (2b_Template_RANKING ES) **(the sheets must be printed in A4 only fronts)**
 - c. Large poster for voting on ES (2c_ES Voting Poster) **(the sheets must be printed in A3 only fronts)**
 - d. Template tables for the selection of indicators (2d_Template_Table Indicators) **(the sheets must be printed in A3 only fronts)**. Make sure you print 1 table per page so that it is not confusing on the day.
2. PPT presentation with some ES examples for you to use during the workshop (optional) (3_Workshop Presentation)
3. Table_Ecosystem Services_Indicators with support information for the facilitators to use if needed (4_Facilitators Supporting Table_Ecosystem Services_indicators)

4. Simple Reporting Template (5_Reporting Template)
5. Attendance Form (6_Registration_WP3 interactive Workshop)
6. Ecosystem Services _Workshop Assessment

<https://forms.gle/fwu24a2ReA7oTAUNA>

OTHER RESOURCES YOU WILL NEED:

- 1 person to act as Main Facilitator
- 4 people to act as table facilitators (depending on the expected number of participants in the workshop)
- Computer
- Projector
- Name tags
- Markers
- Sticky dots
- Post Its

Workshop Roadmap (half a day)/indicative

9:00-9:15	1. Welcome Coffee
Roadmap	Material
The room where the workshop will take place must be organized and prepared to receive the participants.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Name tags 2. Attendance Form (6.Registration_WP3 interactive Workshop)

09:15-10:00	2. Presentation of project and objectives of Workshop
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Plenary Discussion	Material
<p>1. Brief intro to the DIVINFOOD project's general objectives (short and no mention of WPs and Tasks)</p> <p>2. Show the video and discuss with participants the concept of ecosystem services (popularization of the concept with examples that are close to the day-to-day work of participants).</p> <p>3. Discuss why ES are useful for the purposes of their specific LL and how the results of this exercise will be used.</p>	<p>1. Projector</p> <p>2. Computer</p> <p>3. PPT presentation with some ES examples for you to use during the workshop (optional) (3_Workshop Presentation)</p>

10:00-10:15	3. Plenary discussion and presentation of the work plan for the session
Plenary Discussion	Material
<p>1. Explain the work to be developed and the participatory methodologies of the session.</p> <p>2. Collect participants' questions and comments.</p>	<p>1. Projector</p> <p>2. Computer</p> <p>3. PPT presentation with some ES examples for you to use during the workshop (optional) (3_Workshop Presentation)</p>

10:15-10:45	4. 1 st part – Understanding ES
Participants are divided into small groups (divided by sector of activity):	Material
<p>1. The cards are laid out on the table and the facilitator explains the content of each card/ES and which ES will be considered "compulsory" for measurement in the project (Compulsory ES are marked on the cards)</p> <p>2. Each participant has 5 minutes to see the cards and make a list (on a sheet provided for this purpose) in which they rank the cards according to relevance</p> <p>3. Each participant shares their list with the group and explains the reasons for their choice and agree on a final list</p>	<p>2a_PPT_ES CARD GAME - in EN, they will have to be translated</p> <p>2b_Template_RANKING ES</p> <p>Markers</p>

10:45-11:00	5. 2 nd part- Selecting the most relevant ES
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	(maximum 2 votes per participant)
Back in plenary Discussion	Material
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Table facilitators present the results of their tables and a summary of the discussion 2. Main facilitator presents the ES list on a large poster placed on the wall of the room (separating compulsory ES from non compulsory ES - Compulsory ES are marked on the table) 3. Each LL participant will be given 2 votes (colour stickers) to vote on those non mandatory ES they believe are most important/relevant 4. The 2 most voted ES, together with the 3 compulsory ES are those that will be used for indicator selection (3rd part) 	<p>2c_ES Voting Poster</p> <p>Sticky dots</p>

11:00-11:15	Coffee-Break
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11:15-12:30	6. 3rd part- Selecting Indicators for ES
World Cafe Method	Material
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 4/5 tables. Important! each table will work on 1 of the selected Ecosystem Service (top 3/4 or ES) 2. Table facilitator places the ES table with indicators (2d_Template_Table Indicators) on the table, which is already prefilled with indicators (some are compulsory too - Compulsory ES Indicators are marked on the table). 3. Each participant is provided with a few post its to think and write other ideas of indicators that could be used to measure each ES (each participant writes one idea per post it). You can also write directly on the template table. 4. Discussion goes around which indicators would be best or easier to measure. Facilitators make notes on the discussion to present it to the next group. 5. 3 rounds of (15 to 20 min). Participants change table and can freely decide which table to go to, always making sure all tables are covered 	<p>2d_Template_Table Indicators</p> <p>Post its</p> <p>Markers</p>

<p>Note: Indicators should be easy to use in routine and need a minimum of materials to assess the criteria, so that efficient monitoring can be processed with limited cost.</p> <p>Option 2. You may also choose to do this part without people rotating tables and having a longer discussion in each table and various indicators per table. Same method as we used in the annual meeting.</p>	
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<p>12:30-13:00</p>	<p>7. 4th part. Final discussion and establishing responsibilities</p>
<p>In plenary session</p>	<p>Material</p>
<p>1. Table facilitators present in plenary session the result of each table (indicators and ways of measuring them)</p> <p>2. The main Facilitator in the plenary session asks participants who (which farmers) would be interested in measuring these ES and which ones? (facilitator should aim to have different farming systems)</p> <p>3. Facilitator records names of responsible people</p>	<p>2d_Template_Table Indicators</p>

<p>After the workshop</p>	<p>8. Reporting</p>
<p>Reporting Template: table to be completed by LL coordinators after the workshop.</p>	<p>5_Reporting Template)</p>

8.1.2 PPT_ES Card Game

recorte as cartas

Genetic resources*

The genes in plants and animals that are useful to humans are called the gene pool. It's important to keep a variety of different organisms, especially domesticated ones and their ancestors, to have a wide range of genes. The more diverse the genes, the better the ability to adapt to the environment.

*Compulsory ES

Food*

Plants that are grown for food, resources, or energy.

*Compulsory ES

recorte as cartas

recorte as cartas

Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events

Plants on the ground stop the soil from washing away, which is important because when soil gets eroded, it becomes less fertile and can lead to the land becoming like a desert. This also makes it harder to grow crops.

recorte as cartas

Regulation of soil quality

Vegetation cover ensures soil fertility through natural biological processes such as nitrogen fixation. Maintenance of soil quality; legumes used to increase/maintain N-levels in soil. Formation, protection and decontamination of soils and sediments.

 recorte as cartas

Regulating Services
Regulation of baseline flows
and extreme events

 recorte as cartas

Regulating Services
Regulation of soil quality

recorte as cartas

Pollination

Insects and wind help plants and trees reproduce by transferring pollen, which is necessary for fruits, vegetables, and seeds to grow. This is called animal pollination, and it is mostly done by insects, but also by some birds and bats. Pollinators are very important in farms and gardens because they help produce fruits, vegetables, and seeds for various crops. Bees, birds, and bats are some examples of pollinators. They contribute to about 35% of the world's crop production, increasing the output of 75% of the main food crops globally.

recorte as cartas

Pest, disease and seed control*

Predators and parasites in ecosystems help control the populations of pests and disease carriers.

*Compulsory ES

recorte as cartas

recorte as cartas

recorte as cartas

Cultural

Millions of people around the world are drawn to enjoy nature, which provides cultural benefits to visitors and income opportunities for those in the nature tourism industry.

recorte as cartas

Habitat for species

Ecosystems provide homes for plants and animals and support a variety of important processes. Certain habitats have an abundance of species, making them genetically diverse and known as 'biodiversity hotspots'.

 recorte as cartas

 recorte as cartas

8.1.3 Template_ RANKING ES

ES RANKING

Please rank the ES according to their perceived relevance: 1 most relevant to 8 least relevant. And explain the reasons for your choices.

ES	RANKING	WHY?
Food		
Genetic resources		
Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events		
Regulation of soil quality		
Pollination		
Pest, disease, and weed control		
Cultural		
Habitat for species		

Name: _____

Actor Group
(Farmer/Processor/PolicyMakers/..): _____

8.1.4 ES Voting Poster

ES SELECTION

MANDATORY ES	VOTES
Food	?
Genetic resources	?
Pest, disease and weed control	?
NON MANDATORY ES	VOTES
Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	
Regulation of soil quality	
Pollination	
Cultural	
Habitat for species	

8.1.5 Template_Table Indicators

Food

 Compulsory ES and indicators are highlighted

INDICATORS	WAY OF DETERMINATION	WHO WILL MEASURE?
Grain yield 		
Protein yield	Measurement (kg/ha or g/kg) comparing different cultivars on the same field as well as comparing with the main crop(s)	
Other provision indicator relevant for your crop		
Revenue for the farmer		
Clean/Secure/Healthy Production		
Quantity for processing		
Stability of yield, quality and demand		
Food chain Know How		

Genetic resources

? Compulsory ES and indicators are highlighted

INDICATORS	WAY OF DETERMINATION	WHO WILL MEASURE?
Number of cultivated species at farm level within a calendar year ?	Self-declaration by the farmer (estimated number by the farmers across last 3- years) ?	
Number of cultivated NUC species at farm level within a calendar year ?	Self-declaration by the farmer (estimated number by the farmers across last 3- years) ?	
Number of genetically diverse NUC cultivars used within a calendar year ?	Number of landraces, populations, open pollinated varieties (everything that is not a hybrid or pure line variety) ?	

Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events

INDICATORS	WAY OF DETERMINATION	WHO WILL MEASURE?
Percentage of soil cover in cropland	Ratio of crop land with cover crop/ winter crop/grassland and bare soil comparing NUC and main crop outside the growing season. What % and how many ha of the cultivated area is covered outside the growing season? Self-declaration of the farmer (% and ha)	
Soil cover duration	How many months of the year is the NUC and main crop covering the soil? Self-declaration of the farmer	
Type of tillage	What tillage systems are used in case of NUC and main crop production? Please indicate the % ratios. low/minimum/zero/reduced	
Retention capacity of water in agricultural soils	Soil infiltration test (https://www.wineaustralia.com/getmedia/ab39c37e-4f64-4cdb-8ff2-5ee05fe235ff/Infiltration-rates.pdf) Comparing 2 handfuls of soil with water and see how the soil filters it.	
Use of agroforestry within floodplains	Agroforestry uses in case of NUC and main crop (yes/no)	
Amount of biomass	Estimation of the amount of biomass of NUC and main crop compared (estimation)	

Regulation of soil quality

INDICATORS	WAY OF DETERMINATION	WHO WILL MEASURE?
Are there plant residues from previous year on cropland?	Yes/No (What do you do with the plant residues?)	
Qualitative assessment of soil	Spade diagnosis, earworm number/spade. Bait-Lamina Test for soil life indicator (http://www.terra-protecta.de/en/bait_strips.html#0) Mineralisation test (teabag, underwear or example from DIVERIMPACTS--> weaving frames). Weaving frames are very easy to use and should give quite standardized results Earthworm diversity with eQBS	
Fertilizer use	Qualification and quantification of fertilizer use	
pH of topsoil	Paper indicator (eroded soil increases pH)	
Nitrogen provision (fixation)	Evaluate N in the biomass, only for legumes	

Pollination

INDICATORS	WAY OF DETERMINATION	WHO WILL MEASURE?
Simplified measurement of pollinators	e.g. count the number of insects trapped by a simplified trap (example from DIVERIMPACTS), if feasible identify the pollinator species	
Pollination potential	measure seed set of a target plant e.g. sunflower	
Areal coverage of flowering vegetation supporting pollination	Ratio of flowering vegetation to the total farm land (NUC and main crop separately)	
Flowering time	Time period in a calendar year with flowering plants present (NUC and main crop separately)	

Pest, disease and weed control

? Compulsory ES and indicators are highlighted

INDICATORS	WAY OF DETERMINATION	WHO WILL MEASURE?
Provided space for biological pest control (i.e., einkorn vs wheat because of the plant density in the crop stand)	Count nesting birds on NUC and main crop field at a relevant time of the year	
Farming system	Type of plant protection used in case of NUC and main crop	
Level of natural pest and disease resistance of NUC/main crop	Low, medium, high	
Qualification and quantification of plant protection used	Active ingredient and quantity used for NUC and for main crop	
resistant and tolerant cultivars	Number of resistant/tolerant cultivars in case of NUCs and main crop separately used at farm level	
Soil cover = competitive ability of cultivar against weeds--> decrease of chemical weed control ?	At a relevant phase of the NUC as well as main crop, data will be collected separately on % crop cover/ % weed cover/ % bare soil (it can be more than 100%). At flowering and harvest. 1m2 area (at least 3 times): % crop cover/ % weed cover/ % bare soil (it can be more than 100%) ?	
Saved costs on input purchase and hours/fuel/machinery for doing the treatments (€)		
Early Plant Vigor	Canopeo	

Cultural

INDICATORS	WAY OF DETERMINATION	WHO WILL MEASURE?
NUC events as income opportunities for farmers cultivating NUCs	Events related to NUC (number of events, revenue of the events, number of visitors, number of jobs created)	
Cultural value	Number of NUC crops added in the cropping system Number of heritage cultivars/landraces added in the cropping system	
Funding opportunities, as income opportunities for farmers cultivating NUCs	Funding (Number of Research projects, rural development funds, other funds, other advantages like direct marketing, related to NUC, number of jobs created. Compare with main crop	

Habitat for Species

INDICATORS	WAY OF DETERMINATION	WHO WILL MEASURE?
Ecosystem diversity: presence of key wild animal species. Does the presence of the NUC in the field have a known effect on the presence of certain vertebrate animal species (e.g., nesting space by less dense einkorn crop stand vs dense common wheat stand)?	Number of vertebrate animal species (amphibians, birds, mammals) e.g., nesting, feeding in the NUC area compared to main crop area	
Ecosystem diversity. Presence of key wild plants (weeds)	Simple observation (can be done during an open field day involving all stakeholders) e.g., recording with the help of checklist and pictures easily recognisable key plant species, like paper at flowering period. Additionally wild species can be measured via niche available for wild plants--> measured in artificial weed plot (e.g., a 1 qm of mixture of different species to mimic the wild plant)"	
	Landscape design Colours	
	Target species in the region	
	Diversity in insects, animals, birds	
	The requirement of the habitat. Balance with crops	
	Size of the farm	
	Learning (human capital) by doing	

8.1.6 Workshop Presentation.pptx

This project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant Agreement No.101000383

Participatory assessment of ecosystem services of agrobiodiversity in use

DIVINFOOD | Deconstructing infrastructure to build the food chains
to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based FOOD

<p>Please provide a brief reflection on the consecution of the activity, where objectives met?, how did the discussion go?, were objectives and relevance clear to the participants? General observations, improvements</p>	
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Please fill out table with the ES ranking that resulted from the exercise	
Type of actor group	ES Ranking
<i>Ex: Farmers’s Cooperatives and Associations</i>	<i>EX: 1^a Food</i>

Please fill out table with the list of ES and indicators that resulted from the exercise:			
ES selected	Brief explanation for the selection of the ES in relation to project's and LL's objectives	Indicators	Who will be in charge of measuring the indicators

8.1.9 Evaluation Form

Interactive Workshop WP3

Participatory assessment of ecosystem services of agrobiodiversity in use
DD/MM/YY, (Location)

EVALUATION FORM

We would like to take this opportunity to thank you for attending this event. Please take a few minutes to answer this short questionnaire critically. The aim is to get your opinion on how this meeting went. This questionnaire is important to us because it allows us to analyze and improve our performance in future meetings. There are no right or wrong answers; all your opinions and comments are valuable. This questionnaire is confidential and anonymous. Thank you very much!

ON THE MEETING

1. Please indicate how satisfied you were with the structure of the meeting (for ex., sequence of topics, presentation, dynamics). Select the most appropriate option.

1	2	3	4	5
Very unsatisfied				Very satisfied

Do you have any suggestions for improving the structure of this meeting?

2. How innovative is the approach we have presented?

1	2	3	4	5
Not innovative				Very innovative

Please explain or give an example:

3. Do you consider this meeting format to be a good form of communication between the various stakeholders? Yes • No •

8.2 Annex 2: Empirical data on ES indicators collected in DIVINFOOD on-farm trials (season 2)

(Note: Data entries on NUC yield provided in t/ha were converted into kg/m2 for homogenisation purposes)

On-farm sample code	Living Lab	Country	On-farm trial code	NUC cultivar methods, when specified	Mandatory Ecosystem Services (season 2)										
					Food	Genetic Resources			Pest, disease, and weed control						
						NUC yield (kg/m2)	Number of cultivated species at farm level within a calendar year*	Number of cultivated NUC species at farm level within a calendar year*	Number of genetically diverse NUC cultivars used within a calendar year*	Weed coverage (%) of the NUC area during early plant development*	Weed coverage of the NUC area around harvest (%)*	NUC Soil coverage 1. / NUC Early plant vigour (%)	NUC Soil coverage 2. / NUC Biomass (%)		
LL1 France															
1	LL2	France	LL2_1			Garden = many species	No modern cultivars			Garden -> untaken weeds by hand	Garden -> untaken weeds by hand				
2			LL2_2			4	3	> 15							
3	LL3	France	LL3_1		2.19	9	4	30	0.03	7,5					
4			LL3_2		2.28	7	2	22	0.03	7,5					
5	LL4	Switz.	LL4_1	Overall lupin (2 fields, relay intercropping + Seed Treatment trial)	0.254	>15	6	> 4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
6				lupin in intercropping	1.65	>15	6	> 4	NA	70	NA	NA	NA		
7				lupin sole crop in intercrop trial	0.3	>15	6	> 4	NA	10	NA	NA	NA		
8			LL4_2		0.337	6	3	3	NA	20	NA	NA	NA		
9			LL4_3			6	3	3	NA	21	NA	NA	NA		
10			LL4_4		0.28										
11			LL4_5		0.15										
12		LL5	Portugal	LL5_1	70cm w/ Herb.	0.022	1	1	1	na	na	na	na	na	
13					70cm w/o Herb.	0.003	1	1	1	na	na	na	na	na	
14	30cm w/ Herb.				0.135	1	1	1	na	na	na	na	na		
15	30cm w/o Herb.				0.013	1	1	1	na	na	na	na	na		
16				LL5_2			>5	1	1	1	na	na	na	na	
17				LL5_3	70cm w/ Herb.	0.131	>10	3	3	3	na	0.15	na	na	na
18	70cm w/o Herb.				0.101	>10	3	3	3	na	0.15	na	na	na	
19	30cm w/ Herb.				0.211	>10	3	3	3	na	0.15	na	na	na	
20	30cm w/o Herb.				0.093	>10	3	3	3	na	0.15	na	na	na	
21				LL5_4	70cm w/ Herb.	0.056	4	1	1	1	na	na	na	na	na
22	70cm w/o Herb.				0.096	4	1	1	1	na	na	na	na	na	
23	30cm w/ Herb.				0.028	4	1	1	1	na	na	na	na	na	
24	30cm w/o Herb.	0.014	4		1	1	1	na	na	na	na	na			

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				Mandatory Ecosystem Services (season 2)										
				Food	Genetic Resources			Pest, disease, and weed control						
LL6 Denmark														
25	LL7	Sweden	LL7_1	Anicia (low plant density)	0.084	0	7	0	20%	26		79		
26			LL7_1	Anicia (high plant density)	0.134	0	7	0	20%	19		82		
27			LL7_1	Sarnes (low plant density)	0.032	0	7	0	20%	21		66		
28			LL7_1	Beluga (low plant density)	0.166	0	7	0	20%	14		94		
29			LL7_1	Beluga (high plant density)	0.198	0	7	0	20%	10		94		
30			LL7_1	Laird (low plant density)	0.087	0	7	0	20%	19		85		
31			LL7_1	Red Flash (low plant density)	0.131	0	7	0	20%	19		81		
32			LL7_1	Gotlandsblins (low plant density)	0.116	0	7	0	20%	12		82		
33			LL7_1	Gotlandsblins (high plant density)	0.148	0	7	0	20%	12		88		
34			LL7_1	Klaus (low plant density)	0.104	0	7	0	20%	8		86		
					LL7_2			0	0					
35			LL8	Hungary	LL8_1	cowpea	0.6	8-10	4-5	4-5	3-5%	0.3	3.15%	20%
36						black chick pea	1.5	8-10	4-5	4-5	3-5%	0.3	3.15%	20%
37					LL8_2			20	12	1	0	3%	0.3	0.8
38	LL8_3					0.1	5	1	0	3-5%	0.2	0.8	0.95	
39	LL8_4						6	1	0	40-60%	0.8	70,00%	0.99	
40	LL8_5					0.16	7	2	0	30%	0.05	0.7	0.95	
41	LL8_6	snow peas				0.95	25	4	2	0	0	0.5	0.7	
42	LL8_7	sweet horizon				2.6	35	3	3	0	0	0.5	0.7	
43		norli				1	35	3	3	0	0	0.5	0.7	
44		faba						35	3	3	0	0	0.5	0.7
45		yardlong beans						35	3	3	0	0	0.5	0.7
46		LL8_8			Norli		0.02	100	6	2	0	0		
47	Bernhardsberger					0.27	100	6	2	0	0			
48	Aquadulcie					0.08	100	6	2	0	0			
49		Cannetti		0.5	100	6	2	0	0					
50	LL9	Hungary	LL9_1	Grauer		0.13	>5	2	2	32%	50-50%	29%	42%	
51				Búzadi		0.14	>5	2	2	50%	50-50%	29%	40%	
52			LL9_2			0.25	>5	1	1	1-5%		51,8%		
53			LL9_3	GI-2139		0.31	>5	2	2	5-10%		85,3%		
54				Roter		0.34	>5	2	2	1-5%		85,3%		
55			LL9_4				>5	2	2					
56			LL9_5	Nödk alakor		0.2		2	2					
57			LL9_5	Weisser		1.9		2	2					

